

New formulas of Rydberg constant and Bohr radius can be derived

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Abstract: When a theory needs a new explanation, sometimes the first impression of this explanation is absurd.

Key words: universal Gravitational constant formula, Coulomb's law, Basic atomic mass.

I have found everything I can find. I have found that the physical formulas of Rydberg constant and Bohr radius in current physics can be linked to these two formulas, that is,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)^2} = \frac{(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(a_0)} , \\ \frac{[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(a_0)} = (R_\infty) , \end{cases}$$

Then I found that the Rydberg constant and Bohr radius can not be deduced from the most basic mathematical concepts, because at this stage of physics, only $x * y = a$, if we want to deduce X and Y from the first principles, we need to have $x / y = b$. That is,

$$\begin{cases} x * y = a , \\ x / y = b , \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x = ? , \\ y = ? , \end{cases}$$

Then I found that if I want to have $X / y = B$, then it is the following formula. Its numerical value tells me that it is right, its theory tells me that it is self consistent, and the explanation they bring tells me that it can explain the world, but the physical unit tells me that it is wrong. I struggled for a long time, and then decided to accept this reality, because when the theory needs a new explanation, it will bring new impact to people, but it has been written out, and I am willing to believe that it is correct, because the example of fine structure constant tells me that rather than believe that this constant has nothing to do with the physical constant defined by human beings, we should believe that human beings have mistaken its definition. Later, when I thought about it, I felt suddenly enlightened. If it was right, then there would be,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = 2\pi(m_e)[\alpha_0](c) , \\ \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} = (c) , \\ \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2 = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2}{2\pi(R_\infty)} , \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(m_e)(m_{\text{atom}})(G_N)}{(a_0)^2} = (2\pi)^3(m_e)(e_0) , \\ \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} = \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(K_B)} , \\ 2\pi(m_e)(\mu_B) = (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(G_N) * (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(G_N) , \end{array} \right.$$

Where (ϵ_0) is the Vacuum dielectric constant, (μ_0) is the Permeability of vacuum, (c) is the Speed of light, (e_0) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (R_∞) is the Rydberg constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_{atom}) is the Basic atomic mass, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, (G_N) is the Gravitational constant, (μ_B) is the Bohr magneton constant, (k_B) is the Boltzmann constant.

Reference: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Physical_constant.